

Research paper

HFJOINT: A high-fidelity numerical modeling tool for stress concentration factor analysis of welded tubular joints

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ABSTRACT

Assessing the fatigue performance of welded tubular joints is crucial to the safety and durability of their host structures. Fast-computing beam-element models are insufficient to accurately capture local stress concentrations at the intersection region, leading to inaccurate lifetime predictions. In this work, a high-fidelity numerical modeling tool, HFJOINT, is developed for stress concentration analysis of welded tubular joints, following a user-friendly process. The workflow begins with the creation of an elementary T/Y-joint using quadratic hexahedron elements, where the weld geometry is generated in accordance with the American Welding Society (AWS) standard. The chord and brace are divided into several regions allowing for an entirely structured mesh. The geometric transformations of multiple elementary joints enable creating more complex joints. After evaluating the stiffness matrix, the beam-element forces are converted to external tractions, and are transformed into solid-element nodal forces via Gaussian integral. The boundary conditions are defined from the geometric constraints formulated by the Lagrange's equation of the second kind. Based on the nodal displacements, the postprocessing module evaluates the local stress at any point. Using linear extrapolation, the hot-spot structural stress and the stress concentration factors (SCFs) along the weld circumference are computed. The workflow has a computational complexity of $\mathcal{O}(N^{1.89})$. The mesh convergence shows that the relative changes are below 2% when refining the weld circumference from 64 to 96 segments. The tool is verified against the SCFs of benchmark T-, K- and X- joint models, showing its potential for fatigue analysis of welded tubular joints in broad applications.

1. Introduction

Tubular joints with welded connections are used in a variety of complex, large-scale structures such as offshore wind turbines [1] and bridges [2], because of the balance between strength, own weight and ease of fabrication. As shown in Fig. 1, the simplest case of a welded tubular joint consists of a single brace and chord connecting at a certain intersection angle. The cross section of the weld depends on the dihedral angle, which varies along the weld circumference, reaching its maximum at the crown and the minimum at the saddle. Stress concentration at the weld toe in tubular joints is a critical factor governing fatigue life. The weld toe, where the weld meets the base metal, introduces a geometric discontinuity that acts as a stress raiser, leading to localized high stresses. As a result, the lifetime of welded tubular structures is usually governed by the fatigue behavior of their joints [3]. Fatigue experiments on large tubular joints are extremely costly. High-fidelity numerical modeling techniques [4] provide more accurate, efficient and versatile approaches for the fatigue assessment

of tubular joints, but require expertise and are time intensive when a generalized modeling approach is considered.

The numerical modeling of tubular joints has been an active field of research for several decades [5]. For complex structures consisting of a large number of tubular members, global models are conventionally developed using beam elements [6,7]. Such low-fidelity models are computationally efficient, but are insufficient to accurately describe the local stress fields near the welds that govern the fatigue life due to the weld geometry and thin-wall nature. To address the limitation of beam models, shell-element models [8,9] have been introduced, where the geometric features of the tubular walls and their intersection area are presented. However, these models introduce stress singularities at the sharp edges, leading to highly overestimated fatigue stresses. For this reason, the surface stress extrapolation hot-spot structural (HSS) stress approach was proposed to evaluate the stress at the weld toe from the extrapolation of nearby local nodal stresses. To make the trade off between a beam model (computationally efficient) and a shell model

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Nomenclature

$\bar{\sigma}$	The normal stress on a specified 3D plane after coordinate transform of stress tensor
σ	Stress tensor in the vector form
η	The 2nd natural coordinate for Lagrange's or transfinite interpolation
$\bar{\mathbf{r}}$	Local coordinates of an interpolation point in the weld cross section
ϕ_r	Rodrigues' rotation angle of the 3D rotation about a specified axis
ϕ_w	The slope angle of the weld upper surface
Ψ	Dihedral angle between the chord and brace walls
ψ_r	Euler angle for the 3D rotation about global Z axis
ρ	Polar angle of the weld circumference
σ	Normal stress (having the subscripts xx, yy and zz)
σ_{HS}	Hot spot stress at the weld toe
σ_{nm}	Nominal stress evaluated from a beam member
τ	Shear stress (having the subscripts xy, yz and xz)
\mathbf{A}^e	Boolean matrix mapping the element DOFs into the global DOFs list
\mathbf{B}	Element strain matrix
\mathbf{D}	Constitutive matrix of the material
\mathbf{F}	Global nodal force vector
\mathbf{f}	Surface traction field resulting from beam element load
\mathbf{J}	Jacobian matrix from natural coordinates to the physical coordinates
\mathbf{K}	Global stiffness matrix
\mathbf{K}_e	Element stiffness matrix
\mathbf{R}	Coordinate transformation matrix
\mathbf{U}	Global nodal displacement vector
\mathbf{U}_e	Element nodal displacement vector
\mathbf{U}_F	The displacement vector of the DOFs to be solve
\mathbf{U}_{im}	The global imposed displacement vector
\mathbf{U}_I	The displacement vector of the imposed DOFs
θ	brace intersection angle
θ_r	Euler angle for the 3D rotation about global Y axis
φ_r	Euler angle for the 3D rotation about global X axis
$\bar{\mathbf{e}}_j$	The unit direction vectors for the local coordinate system of the weld cross section ($j = 1, 2, 3$)
$\bar{\mathbf{n}}$	Normal unit vector of a reference plane
$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_0$	The global coordinates of a given point at the top surface of the weld.
$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{[...]}$	Global coordinates of the points in a transfinite mesh, where the subscripts T/B/L/R denotes top/bottom/left/right edges, respectively, and the subscripts 1/2/3/4 denotes the corner nodes
$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{cb}$	Global coordinates of the points at the inner surface of the chord
$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{ct}$	Global coordinates of the points at the outer surface of the chord

$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_c$	Global coordinates of the node at the reference plane of the brace
$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{ht}$	Global coordinates of the points at the interface between B-HS and B-TR regions
$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{I_1}$	Intersection line between chord and brace (inner side)
$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{I_2}$	Intersection line between chord and brace (outer side)
$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_I$	Intersection line between two cylinders (outer side)
$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{mi}$	Global coordinate of a point symmetric about a specified reference plane
$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{mv}$	Global coordinate of a point after 3D rotation
$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{mv}$	Global coordinate of a point after translational moving
$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_t$	Global coordinates of the points at the top of the B-UN region
$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_v$	A vector containing the coordinate of the weld vertices
$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{w0}$	The global coordinates of the inner intersection point (I_1) of the weld cross section
$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{ij}$	Coordinates of the weld interpolation points in the local coordinate system
ξ	The 1st natural coordinate for Lagrange's or transfinite interpolation
$\bar{\Xi}_j$	A geometry sequence for a transition mesh where the element sizes gradually change.
ζ	The 3rd natural coordinate for Lagrange's or transfinite interpolation
A	Area of the cross section
b_{cts}	Width of the chord transition region
F_{ax}	Axial force applied on a beam member
F_{ips}	In-plane shear force applied on a beam member
F_{ops}	Out-of-plane shear force applied on a beam member
I	Moment of inertia of the cross section
L	Total length of the chord
L_{bu}	The axial length of the B-UN region
L_h	The distance from the joint center to the reference plane of the brace
M_{ipb}	In-plane bending moment applied on a beam member
M_{opb}	Out-of-plane bending moment applied on a beam member
N_j	The bilinear interpolation functions for the mesh grid of weld cross section ($j = 1, 2, 3, 4$)
n_{bhs}	Number of elements along the axis of the brace hot-spot region
n_e	Total number of elements in a finite element mesh
n_n	Total number of nodes in a finite element mesh
q	The factor describing the steepness of the changing element sizes in a transition mesh.
R	Outer radius of the chord cross section
r	Outer radius of the brace cross section
R_w	The gap in height between the chord and brace
T_b	Torsional moment applied on a beam member
t_w	The thickness of the weld cross section
w	Weight factors for the Gaussian numerical integral

x_j	The distance from the stress extrapolation point to the weld toe ($j = 1, 2$)
y_c	Distance from a specified point to the neutral surface

(accurate), the stress concentration factor (SCF) [10], characterizing the ratio between the shell HSS stress and the beam nominal stress, is used. In engineering design, the SCFs are determined from empirical parametric equations (e.g., the Efthymiou equation [11]) that are fitted to simulation data and validated with limited experiment data. Therefore, these parametric equations have inherent limitations. Due to the involved exponential functions, the accuracy of the formulae is significantly reduced when a part of the parameters are outside their validity ranges [12]. With increasing computation power, high-fidelity solid-element modeling offers a robust solution for exactly taken into account the complex geometries of tubular joints [13–15]. This allows for the consideration of the detailed shape of the weld cross-section, for example based on the American Welding Society (AWS) standard [16]. Such high-fidelity models typically use 8-node linear [17] or 20-node quadratic hexahedron [13] elements which are available in commercial finite element software packages like Abaqus [18,19], Ansys [20,21] and Comsol [22]. In most cases, a linear-element mesh is generated, namely the raw mesh [23], and is then upgraded to a 20-node quadratic-element mesh, where the added edge nodes are conventionally assumed at the middle positions. High-fidelity modeling in fatigue assessments of welded tubular joints presents several challenges that remain to be addressed:

- (i) Mesh quality control. Due to the complex geometry, non-structured meshes are usually considered for the sake of convenience and adaptivity. This may, however, result in distorted elements which affect the precision of computation. A fine, high-quality mesh near the weld is required in order to capture the high stress gradient and related stress concentration [24]. Conversely, the global mesh size should ideally be relatively coarse in order to limit the computational cost. This further increases the difficulty in mesh quality control. An alternative approach is to divide the joint into a number of simpler pieces, ensuring that a tailored structured mesh is possible for each of the pieces [23]. The meshed pieces are then merged to form a meshed representation of the entire joint. However, a complex transition scheme remains needed to connect the fine mesh zone near the weld and the far-field zone having a coarser mesh, especially for the compatibility along the thickness direction.
- (ii) Trade off between accuracy and computational efficiency. The 8-node linear hexahedron and 20-node serendipity hexahedron (where the cross terms are omitted from its shape functions) elements provided in most softwares are insufficient to present the internal stress gradient without a very refined mesh. The complete quadratic hexahedron element has higher accuracy in describing large stress gradients, having potential in handling stress-concentration problems [25], but a larger number of DOFs have to be included.
- (iii) Complicated workflow. The SCF analysis of a welded tubular joint involves multiple steps including geometric modeling [26], mesh generation, load definition, static solver and surface stress extrapolated HSS stress determination. These refer to the interaction between multiple software tools and considerable manual interventions, which are challenging to handle, especially for non-expert users.

It can be concluded that most modeling techniques are limited in accurately capturing the weld geometry, creating a high-quality mesh and performing a stress concentration analysis. To address these

challenges, a structured mesh strategy based on 27-node completely quadratic hexahedron elements (Hexa27n), along with the solver for evaluating the stress field and SCFs, is proposed in the present work. It allows for the numerical modeling and fatigue assessment of welded tubular joints using a semi-automatic, user-friendly and controllable approach. In the proposed mesh strategy, a joint is always modeled from the integration of one or multiple T/Y-joints (which is called elementary joints in the following). Such elementary joint is divided into a number of interconnecting regions. Some regions are further divided into a number of parts allowing for structured mesh through either linear or transfinite interpolation in the 3D space. The high-fidelity model of the elementary joint is then obtained by merging the structured Hexa27n meshes of all parts. This supports the modeling of more complex multi-brace, multi-planar tubular joints by creating, transforming and merging multiple elementary joints. By considering the boundary conditions from geometric constraints and element surface tractions (e.g., the distributed stress converted from beam-element forces), the stress field of the joint can be solved, allowing for the evaluation of hot-spot stresses and stress concentration factors along the full circumference of the weld. The proposed methodology has been integrated into a novel tool called 'high-fidelity numerical modeling of welded tubular joints (HFJOINT)'. The tool presents a user-friendly interface for (semi)-automatic generation of Hexa27n models of welded tubular joints, allowing engineers to accurately perform SCF calculations for a variety of actual joint geometries without being affected by the validity limitations of empirical formulae.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. The high-fidelity model generation of an elementary joint is demonstrated in Section 2. Based on the geometric transformations of elementary joints, the modeling of complex joints is illustrated in Section 3. The finite element formulation, involving the stiffness matrix, geometric constraints, the force vector and the evaluations of stress field and SCFs, is derived in Section 4. The SCFs evaluated from the developed HFJOINT are verified by means of case studies in Section 5, including a benchmark T-joint model for mesh refinement, computational cost and accuracy, as well as both X- and K-joints for comparison with experiment data. Finally, conclusions are made in Section 6

2. Structured mesh of an elementary joint

In this section, the mesh generation of an elementary joint (i.e., a T- or Y-joint having a single pair of chord and brace) will be demonstrated. First of all, a subdivision with respect to the member, region and part levels, is applied on the elementary joint (Fig. 2) in order to cope with the geometric complexity.

In HFJOINT convention, the elementary joint is partitioned into brace, weld and chord members. The brace is divided into the hot-spot region (B-HS) having a refined mesh, the uniform region (B-UN) having a coarser mesh and the transition region (B-TR) where the mesh size is gradually varying. The chord is divided into the plug region (C-PL) at the center, the hot-spot region (C-HS) below the weld, the transition region (C-TR) having an edge varying from circle-like to quadrilateral-like, and the extend region (C-EXT). The C-PL region is further divided into the center part (C-PL-CT) and the transition part (C-PL-TR). The C-EXT region is further divided into four parts towards the X-negative (C-EXT-Xn), X-positive (C-EXT-Xp), Z-negative (C-EXT-Zn), and Z-positive (C-EXT-Zp) directions. Based on this strategy, each destination (part/region) can always be modeled from a perfect structured mesh using hexahedron elements.

Considering the accuracy, adaptability and computational efficiency, a complete Lagrange's 27-node quadratic hexahedron (Hexa27n) element (Fig. 3), is developed and is employed by default in HFJOINT. The convention of the node numbering and the natural coordinates of the nodes are listed in Table A.5. The structured mesh for each region/part will be demonstrated next.

Fig. 1. Geometric features of a representative welded tubular joint: (a) overview of the joint; (b) close-up view at the intersection between brace and chord walls.

Fig. 2. Subdivision strategy of an elementary joint in terms of member, region and part levels.

2.1. Weld

In order to properly locate the discretized weld cross sections, the global coordinate system (GCS) (X-Y-Z in Fig. 4(a)) is defined to describe the geometry of the entire joint. The center of the GCS is placed at the intersection point of the chord-brace axes. The X-axis is parallel with the central axis of the chord. The Y-axis is inside the plane of the chord-brace axes and is meantime perpendicular to the X-axis. The Z-axis (out-of-plane) can then be determined by the right-hand rule. In the GCS, the overall geometric shape of the weld is governed by the intersection lines I_1 (between the inner surface of the brace and the outer surface of the chord) and I_2 (between the outer surface of the brace and the outer surface of the chord).

To describe the position of a weld cross-section, the polar angle ρ is defined where $\rho = 0$ indicates the crown at the positive X-side (recall Fig. 1(a)) and ρ increases with the rotation about the global Y-axis. The outer intersection line between two cylinders having the radius R (chord) and r (brace) can be described by the parametric function [27]:

$$\vec{r}_1 = \left(\frac{1}{\sin \theta} \left\{ r \sin \rho - \left[R - \sqrt{R^2 - r^2 \cos^2 \rho} \right] \cos \theta \right\}, \sqrt{R^2 - r^2 \cos^2 \rho}, r \cos \rho \right) \quad (1)$$

where θ is the brace intersection angle which has been denoted in Fig. 1(a). At each polar angle, a local coordinate system is attached to the

Fig. 3. The 27-node quadratic hexahedron element used in HFJOINT: (a) an example in the global coordinate system; (b) ordering of the nodes in the natural coordinate system.

Fig. 4. Geometric profile of the weld: (a) position and orientation in the global coordinate system; (b) shape of the cross-section in the local coordinate system.

weld cross section, see Fig. 4(b). The radial unit vector:

$$\bar{\mathbf{e}}_1 = \frac{\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{I_2} - \bar{\mathbf{r}}_{I_1}}{\|\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{I_2} - \bar{\mathbf{r}}_{I_1}\|} \quad (2)$$

is pointing from I_1 to I_2 , where both $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{I_1}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{I_2}$ are evaluated from Eq. (1) but the brace radius r is taken $r - t$ (where t is the thickness of the brace) and r , respectively. The tangent unit vector:

$$\bar{\mathbf{e}}_2 = \frac{1}{\|d\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{I_1}/d\rho\|} \frac{d\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{I_1}}{d\rho} \quad (3)$$

is pointing in the tangent direction of the inner intersection line, where,

$$\frac{d\bar{\mathbf{r}}_1}{d\rho} = \left(\frac{1}{\sin \theta} \left\{ r \cos \rho + \frac{r^2 \sin \rho \cos \rho \cos \theta}{\sqrt{R^2 - r^2 \cos^2 \rho}} \right\}, \frac{r^2 \sin \rho \cos \rho}{\sqrt{R^2 - r^2 \cos^2 \rho}}, -r \sin \rho \right) \quad (4)$$

is explicitly derived from Eq. (1) using the chain rule. The upward unit vector:

$$\bar{\mathbf{e}}_3 = \bar{\mathbf{e}}_1 \times \bar{\mathbf{e}}_2 \quad (5)$$

is perpendicular to the previous two. The shape of the weld cross-section can then be described within the planar coordinate $\bar{\mathbf{e}}_1 - \bar{\mathbf{e}}_3$, as shown with the red and green arrows in Fig. 4(b). In the local coordinate system of the weld cross-section, a set of geometric relationships governing the shape of the weld cross section are proposed in the AWS standard D1.1:2025 [16]. For complete joint penetration (CJP) welds, the detailed cross-section features depend on the dihedral angle Ψ (the spatial angle between $\bar{\mathbf{e}}_1$ and the brace axis which can be found in Fig. 1(b)), as shown in Fig. 5.

Within the LCS of the weld cross-section, the geometric dimensions shown in Fig. 5 allow to solve the coordinates of the vertices I_2 , A, B,

C, D and E, based on the original point $I_1(0,0)$. Taking detail B (Fig. 5(b)) as an example, the coordinates can be calculated from:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mathbf{r}}_{I_2} &= \left(\frac{t_w}{\sin \psi}, 0 \right), \quad \bar{\mathbf{r}}_A = \left(\frac{R_w}{\tan \psi}, 0 \right), \quad \bar{\mathbf{r}}_B = \left(\frac{R_w}{\tan \psi}, R_w \right), \\ \bar{\mathbf{r}}_C &= (0, R_w), \quad \bar{\mathbf{r}}_E = \left(h_w + \frac{t_w + F_w}{\sin \psi}, 0 \right) \\ \bar{\mathbf{r}}_D &= \left(\frac{t}{\sin \psi} + \frac{\cos \psi (t \tan \phi_w / \sin \psi + R_w)}{\sin \psi - \cos \psi \tan \phi_w}, R_w + \frac{\sin \psi (t \tan \phi_w / \sin \psi + R_w)}{\sin \psi - \cos \psi \tan \phi_w} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where t_w is the thickness of the weld cross section, ϕ_w is the slope angle of the weld upper surface, R_w is the gap in height between the chord and brace. Since the purpose of the model is to determine the local elastic stress fields along the brace-chord intersection as input to high-cycle fatigue analyses, the finite element simulations will be performed considering linear elastic material behavior. It is fair to assume that the linear elastic material properties of the base and weld material are the same. In that case, only the convex envelope of the weld cross-section has to be modeled. The weld cross-section can thus be characterized by the vertices A, B, D and E (Fig. 4(b)). Such cross-section can then be meshed into a structured grid through the bilinear interpolation:

$$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{ij} = \left(\{N_1, N_2, N_3, N_4\} \Big|_{\xi=\xi_i, \eta=\eta_j} \otimes \mathbf{I}^{2 \times 2} \right) \bar{\mathbf{r}}_v \quad (7)$$

where the interpolation functions, in terms of discrete (ξ, η) points, are evaluated by:

$$N_1 = \frac{1}{4}(1 - \xi)(1 - \eta) \quad (8)$$

$$N_2 = \frac{1}{4}(1 - \xi)(1 + \eta) \quad (9)$$

Fig. 5. The geometries of the weld cross-sections [28] with respect to the range of the dihedral angle ψ : (a) detail A; (b) detail B blunt (left) and B sharp (right); (c) detail C; (d) transition from C to D; (e) detail D.

$$N_3 = \frac{1}{4}(1 + \xi)(1 - \eta) \quad (10)$$

$$N_4 = \frac{1}{4}(1 + \xi)(1 + \eta) \quad (11)$$

and the coordinates of the vertices are collected as:

$$\vec{\mathbf{r}}_v = \{x_A, y_A, x_B, y_B, x_D, y_D, x_E, y_E\}^T \quad (12)$$

After obtaining the local coordinates of each node, $\vec{\mathbf{r}}_i$, the positions of the nodes within the global coordinate system, $\vec{\mathbf{r}}$, can be evaluated through a translational motion (ensuring that the point I_1 is exactly at the inner intersection point $\vec{\mathbf{r}}_{w0}$) and a 3D rotation (ensuring that all the unit vectors are pointing to the correct directions). This is implemented by the coordinate transformation:

$$\vec{\mathbf{r}} = \vec{\mathbf{r}}_{w0} + \mathbf{R}\vec{\mathbf{r}} \quad (13)$$

where

$$\mathbf{R} = \{\vec{\mathbf{e}}_1, \vec{\mathbf{e}}_2, \vec{\mathbf{e}}_3\}^T \quad (14)$$

is the 3D rotation matrix from the global coordinate system to the local coordinate system.

2.2. Brace

As mentioned in Fig. 2, the brace is divided into three regions: B-HS (hot-spot region), B-TR (transition region) and B-UN (uniformly meshed region). For the sake of convenience, a reference plane containing the interface between the B-TR and B-UN regions is defined by its normal vector $\vec{\mathbf{n}} = (\cos \theta, \sin \theta, 0)$ and the point at the center of the cross section $\vec{\mathbf{r}}_c = (x_c, y_c, z_c)$ (Fig. 7).

For each node at the top surface of the weld, denoted by $\vec{\mathbf{r}}_0 = (x_0, y_0, z_0)$, the corresponding node at the reference plane is:

$$\vec{\mathbf{r}}_c = \vec{\mathbf{r}}_0 + (L - x_0 \cos \theta - y_0 \sin \theta)\vec{\mathbf{n}} \quad (15)$$

In addition to the reference plane, the nodes at the interface between the B-HS and B-TR regions, $\vec{\mathbf{r}}_{ht}$, as well as the nodes at the top surface of the B-UN region, $\vec{\mathbf{r}}_t$, are:

$$\vec{\mathbf{r}}_{ht} = \vec{\mathbf{r}}_0 + L_h\vec{\mathbf{n}} \quad (16)$$

$$\vec{\mathbf{r}}_t = \vec{\mathbf{r}}_c + L_{bu}\vec{\mathbf{n}} \quad (17)$$

where L_h is the distance between the joint center (i.e., the origin of the global coordinate system) and the center of the reference plane, and L_{bu} is the axial length of the B-UN region. Based on this, the nodes within the B-HS region and B-UN region can be obtained from uniform interpolations between $\vec{\mathbf{r}}_0$ and $\vec{\mathbf{r}}_{ht}$, and between $\vec{\mathbf{r}}_c$ and $\vec{\mathbf{r}}_t$, respectively. The nodes within the B-TR region can be evaluated by using a linear mapping from a geometry sequence between 0 and 1:

$$\vec{\Xi}_j = \frac{1 - q^{j-1}}{1 - q^n} \quad (18)$$

to the physical coordinates between $\vec{\mathbf{r}}_{ht}$ and $\vec{\mathbf{r}}_{ref}$, where q is the factor to describe the steepness of the changing element sizes which is usually taken between 1.05 and 1.50. Consider a case where the regions are respectively divided into 6, 15, 100 layers and the factor $q = 1.20$, an example of the brace mesh is shown in Fig. 8. It is noticed that the bottom nodes of the brace are exactly overlapped with the upper nodes of the weld.

2.3. Chord

As mentioned in [27], among others, the geometry of the chord can be obtained by wrapping a rectangular plate, and the grid points of the plate can be simply generated through uniform discretizations

Fig. 6. Example of a structured mesh of a tubular joint weld profile using tri-quadratic hexahedron elements ($n_p = 24$, $n_z = 1$, $n_\eta = 1$): (a) Global shape of the weld; (b) a close-up view of the weld cross section at $z = 0$ with the unit vectors of the local coordinate system.

Fig. 7. Node mapping from the top surface of the weld to the reference plane at the top surface of the transition region.

with respect to the length (axial), width (circumferential) and thickness directions. For the modeling of tubular joints, specifically, the nodes at the bottom surface of the weld should also be present on the chord. This is difficult to perfectly fulfill from such a uniform discretization with hexahedron elements. Therefore, the chord is partitioned into a number of regions/pieces (recall Fig. 2. Each of the regions/pieces will next be discretized by a structured mesh using Hexa27n elements.

2.3.1. Chord hot-spot region (C-HS)

Attached to the bottom of the weld, the C-HS zone will be created with a refined element mesh, in order to allow extraction of the HSS stress near the weld toe. At each polar angle, the nodes at the bottom of the weld are taken. Based on this, another two reference points P_{in} and P_{out} are created, representing the inner and outer boundaries of the C-HS zone. The coordinates of P_{in} and P_{out} can be evaluated from Eq. (13) where the brace radius r is replaced by $r - t - b_{in}$ and $r + b_{out}$, respectively. The parameters b_{in} and b_{out} characterizing the width of the C-HS zone are automatically determined as $b_{in} = b_{out} = 2t_{chord}$ by default, which are sufficient to include the local stress points for the

hot-spot stress extrapolation in most of the cases. But still, these are included in the optional parameters where the users are allowed to select their specified values. A total number of n_{in} uniformly discrete points are then generated between P_{in} and E (weld), as well as n_{out} points between A (weld) and P_{out} . The inside and outside parts are then discretized into n_{in} and n_{out} elements along the radial direction. For a given node \vec{r}_i at the outer surface of the chord (which has been generated from the above), the coordinates of the corresponding node at the inner surface can be calculated by:

$$\vec{r}_{cb} = \vec{r}_{ct} - \left(\sqrt{y_{ct}^2 + z_{ct}^2} - R + T \right) \vec{n} \quad (19)$$

where

$$\vec{n} = \frac{\{0, y_i, z_i\}^T}{\sqrt{y_i^2 + z_i^2}} \quad (20)$$

is the unit vector pointing in the outward radial direction of the chord tubular. Based on the weld model shown in Fig. 6, an example of the attached connection zone is shown in Fig. 9.

2.3.2. Chord plug region (C-PL)

For the plug zone, the grid points are first generated on a flat plane. The exact spatial points in the X - Y - Z coordinate system are subsequently obtained from the coordinate transformation from the flat plane into a cylinder. Given that the geometry of the plug zone takes the same topological feature of a circular plate, the structured mesh cannot be made by directly using hexahedron elements for a uniform grid. In such case, the plug zone has to be further divided into the central part (C-PL-CT) and the transition part (C-PL-TR). The C-PL-CT part having the same topological feature as a rectangular plate is created through a uniform grid. The C-PL-TR part can be further divided into four meshes. As can be seen from Fig. 10, the geometry of each piece is a curvilinear trapezium, while it should be noticed that one of the edges is curved because the outer edge takes the shape of the intersection line.

Therefore, each mesh can be generated based on a number of quadrilaterals, where the coordinates of the grid points are evaluated from the transfinite interpolation:

$$\vec{r} = (1 - \xi)\vec{r}_1 + \xi\vec{r}_2 + (1 - \eta)\vec{r}_3 + \eta\vec{r}_4 - (1 - \xi)(1 - \eta)\vec{r}_1 - \eta(1 - \xi)\vec{r}_2 - \xi\eta\vec{r}_3 - \xi(1 - \eta)\vec{r}_4 \quad (21)$$

based on a structured grid on the ξ - η plane, where \vec{r}_1 , \vec{r}_2 , \vec{r}_3 and \vec{r}_4 are the x - y coordinates of the corner points, and the coordinates of the edge points are calculated by:

$$\vec{r}_i = f(\rho, r, R) \quad (22)$$

$$\vec{r}_b = (1 - \xi)\vec{r}_1 + \xi\vec{r}_4 \quad (23)$$

$$\vec{r}_l = (1 - \eta)\vec{r}_1 + \eta\vec{r}_2 \quad (24)$$

Fig. 8. Example of a structured mesh of a brace ($n_1 = 3, n_2 = 7, n_3 = 6, q = 1.20$): (a) overview of the brace connected to the weld; (b) a close-up view of the cross section at $z = 0$ with the interface to the weld.

Fig. 9. Example of a structured mesh of a chord C-HS region ($n_{in} = 2, n_{out} = 3$) attached to the underside of the weld: (a) global geometry of the chord connection zone; (b) cross section at the plane $z = 0$.

Fig. 10. Subdivision of the C-PL-TR part into four transfinite meshes: (a) overview of the mesh strategy; (b) computational domain $\xi-\eta$ for the transfinite interpolation of the transfinite mesh II as an example.

Fig. 11. Example of a structured mesh of a chord connection zone ($n_{in} = 2$, $n_{out} = 3$) attached below the weld: (a) overall geometry of the chord connection zone; (b) cross section at the plane $z = 0$.

Fig. 12. Subdivision of the C-TR region into eight transfinite meshes: (a) overview of the mesh generation; (b) computational domain ξ - η for the transfinite interpolation of the mesh I as an example.

$$\vec{r}_r = (1 - \eta)\vec{r}_4 + \eta\vec{r}_3 \quad (25)$$

By uniformly discretizing the plug transition zone into three intervals in the computational domain, an example of the entire plug zone connecting with the connection zone is shown in Fig. 11.

2.3.3. Chord transition region (C-TR)

For the chord, a transition region extending outward from the hot-spot region is defined, where its edge gradually changes from a smooth curve (overlapping with the outer surface of the connection zone) into four distinct boundary curves. In order to generate a quadrilateral mesh on the reference flat plane, the transition zone is subdivided into eight transfinite meshes as shown in Fig. 12. For each mesh, the grid points of a structured mesh can be generated from the transfinite interpolation through Eqs. (21)–(25).

As the main focus of the developed model is the stress field near the weld, the element sizes at the locations far away from the weld are allowed to be larger without loss of accuracy. Being different from the plug zone (see Fig. 10(b)), the grid points along the η axis, i.e., the radial direction, are therefore generated as a geometry sequence (from Eq. (18)) instead of a uniform grid in the computational domain, while it should be noted that the number of elements along the circumferential direction $n_\xi = n_\rho/8$ is not independent. After mapping the grid points from the planar coordinate system ξ - η to the 3D spatial coordinate system X - Y - Z , the structured mesh of the transition zone is generated, as shown in Fig. 13.

It has to be mentioned that the size of the C-TR region cannot be too large, in order to avoid the distortion of elements far away from the origin due to the coordinate transformation wrapping the reference flat plate into a cylinder.

2.3.4. Chord extended region (C-EXT)

Based on the outer edges of the C-TR region as shown in Fig. 13, the regular structured meshes will be created by extending these edges outward with a certain space interval. First, the edges parallel to the X -axis will be extended along the positive and negative Z -directions, which forms the grid points along the circumferential direction (i.e., C-EXT-Zp and C-EXT-Zn parts, respectively). Similarly, the edges perpendicular to the X -axis, resulting from the C-TR, C-EXT-Zn and C-EXT-Zp, are combined and are extended along the positive and negative X -directions, which form the C-EXT-Xp and C-EXT-Xn parts, respectively. An example of the C-EXT region is shown in Fig. 14.

2.4. Merge multiple meshes

Once all the meshed regions/parts have been generated (from Sections 2.1–2.3), the entire model of the elementary joint can be created by merging together all the meshes through node sharing at their interfaces. Such operation includes the following steps:

1. Model combination: For the main mesh and an added mesh, the nodal coordinates are collected in the 3-column matrices

Fig. 13. Example of a structured mesh of a C-TR region ($n_\eta = 3$, $q = 1.15$) attached outside the C-HS region: (a) overall geometry of the mesh; (b) a close-up view to the cross section at the plane $z = 0$.

Fig. 14. Example of the C-EXT region connected to the existing C-TR region of the chord.

$nodes_{(main)}$ and $nodes_{(add)}$, respectively. The element connectivities are described by the 27-column (for Hexa27n) matrices $elements_{(main)}$ and $elements_{(add)}$, respectively. The first step is to simply stack the node information and the element connectivities such that the added mesh has been included into the main mesh:

$$nodes = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} nodes_{(main)} \\ nodes_{(add)} \end{array} \right\} \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_n^{(main)} + n_n^{(add)}) \times 3} \quad (26)$$

$$elements = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} elements_{(main)} \\ elements_{(add)} + n_n^{(main)} \end{array} \right\} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{(n_e^{(main)} + n_e^{(add)}) \times 27} \quad (27)$$

where $n_n^{(main)}$ and $n_e^{(main)}$ are respectively the total numbers of nodes and elements in the main mesh, $n_n^{(add)}$ and $n_e^{(add)}$ are respectively the total numbers of nodes and elements in the added mesh.

2. Node sharing: A list named “*node_update*” is initiated as an integer series from 1 to $n_n^{(main)} + n_n^{(add)}$. For each node in the added mesh, its distance to each of the nodes in the main mesh will be evaluated. If a distance smaller than the defined tolerance (which is 10^{-6} by default) is detected, the number of the overlapping node in the main mesh will be recorded in the second column. Based on the overlapping node pairs that have been identified, a mapping manipulation will be performed on the list named “*elements*”, where all overlapping nodes in the added mesh will be replaced by their corresponding nodes in the main mesh. In such case, the main and added meshes are physically connected.

3. Delete unused nodes: Another list named “*node_unique*” is initiated by collecting all the values in “*elements*” from smallest to largest, and an integer series is created in the second column. Based on this, the unused nodes are then deleted by reserving the nodes which have been involved in the first column of “*node_unique*”, and the element connectivities, i.e., “*elements*”, are then updated from a mapping manipulation from the values in the first column of “*node_unique*” to its second column.

From the above, the Hexa27n mesh of an elementary joint can be generated as long as five mandatory parameters (r , t , R , T , θ) have been specified. The T-joint is in fact a particular case for $\theta = 90^\circ$. Such elementary joint will be later used as a fundamental basis for the modeling of more complex joints. In HFJOINT, a total number of 32 parameters are used to describe the geometry of the elementary joint. These include 5 mandatory parameters which must be provided by the user, as well as 27 optional parameters which will be taken by default if not specified. The detailed explanations of the parameters are listed in Appendix B. After defining the parameters, the users may generate the Hexa27n mesh of the elementary joint, as shown in Fig. 15. The node coordinates and element connectivities can be saved as a .pkl file.

3. Modeling of complex joints

For complex joints having multiple tubular members, their high-fidelity models can be developed by adding multiple elementary joints into the main mesh. In order to place the elementary joint at the correct position and orientation, three basic transformations are defined in HFJOINT. For the translational motion, all nodes are moved along

Fig. 15. Graphical user interface (GUI) for generating elementary joints.

the same direction with the same distance. The nodal coordinates are calculated as follows:

$$\vec{r}_{mv} = \vec{r}_0 + D\vec{t} \quad (28)$$

where D is the translation distance and \vec{t} is the unit vector of the translation. The 3D rotation can be defined by its Euler angles φ_r , θ and ψ about the global x , y and z axes, respectively. Given the specified values of the rotational angles, the nodal coordinates after the 3D rotation can be evaluated by:

$$\vec{r}_{rt} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \psi_r & -\sin \psi_r & 0 \\ \sin \psi_r & \cos \psi_r & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_r & 0 & \sin \theta_r \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin \theta_r & 0 & \cos \theta_r \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \varphi_r & -\sin \varphi_r \\ 0 & \sin \varphi_r & \cos \varphi_r \end{bmatrix} \vec{r}_0 \quad (29)$$

Alternatively, such 3D rotation can also be defined as a scalar angle ϕ_r about a specified axis described by its direction vector \vec{t} and a known point \vec{r}_p . In such case, the nodal coordinates after the rotation can be evaluated by the Rodrigues' rotation formula:

$$\vec{r}_{rt} = \vec{r}_0 + (\vec{r}_0 - \vec{r}_p) \cos \phi_r + [\vec{t} \times (\vec{r}_0 - \vec{r}_p)] \sin \phi_r + \vec{t} [\vec{t} \cdot (\vec{r}_0 - \vec{r}_p)] (1 - \cos \phi_r) \quad (30)$$

For a 3D plane described by its normal unit vector \vec{n} and a reference point \vec{r}_p on the plane, the elementary joint can be mapped into a symmetric copy across the plane. The nodal coordinates of the transformed model can be evaluated by:

$$\vec{r}_{mi} = \vec{r}_0 - 2h\vec{n} \quad (31)$$

where

$$h = (\vec{r}_0 - \vec{r}_p) \cdot \vec{n} \quad (32)$$

is the distance from the original node to the symmetry plane. Based on the elementary joints and the transformations, a variety of tubular joints with more complex geometric features can be modeled, as shown in Fig. 16

After the transformation of each elementary joint, the new meshed grid (described by nodal coordinates and element connectivities) is

added into the main mesh through the “merge” function mentioned in Section 2.4, and the final integrated joint model is described by the lists “nodes” and “elements” of the entire model. For the current version of HFJOINT, it is required that the welds should not be overlapping between two elementary joints, such that the interface is created on either the chord or the brace.

4. Finite element formulation

Once the model has been constructed, its stiffness matrix will be evaluated. The external loads including the nodal forces and imposed displacements can either be converted from an associated beam-element model or can be defined by the users. The solver allows to return the displacement, stress and strain values for the entire model.

4.1. Stiffness matrix

From the fundamental finite element theory, the global stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} of the model is obtained from the linear superposition of each element stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_e :

$$\mathbf{K} = \sum_{e=1}^{N_e} \mathbf{A}_e^T \mathbf{K}_e \mathbf{A}_e \quad (33)$$

where \mathbf{A}_e is the Boolean matrix which maps the local DOFs of the e th element to the global system. For each element, the element stiffness matrix is evaluated from the Gaussian quadrature:

$$\mathbf{K}_e = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B} d\Omega \approx \sum_{i=1}^{N_G} \sum_{j=1}^{N_G} \sum_{k=1}^{N_G} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B} | \det(\mathbf{J}) | \Big|_{\xi=g_i, \eta=g_j, \zeta=g_k} w_i w_j w_k \quad (34)$$

where \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{D} and \mathbf{J} are the strain matrix, constitutive matrix and Jacobian matrix, respectively. The locations of the Gauss points and the weight factors are denoted by g and w , respectively. In this work, the correctness of the global stiffness matrix will be checked ensuring that: (i) the values at the diagonal positions are all non-zero ($\prod_{i=1}^N K(i, i) \neq 0$) in order to avoid unused free nodes, and, (ii) the matrix is symmetric ($\max(\text{abs}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}^T)) < \text{tol}$). Due to inevitable truncation errors, the stiffness matrix may not be perfectly symmetric. Therefore, the matrix is imposed to be symmetric by eliminating the deviations:

$$\mathbf{K} \leftarrow \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{K}^T + \mathbf{K}) \quad (35)$$

Fig. 16. High-fidelity modeling of typical tubular joints listed in [1].

Fig. 17. Load mapping from beam-element forces to Hexa27n nodal forces: (a) forces applied on the beam cross section; (b) equivalent nodal forces to be evaluated on the loaded surface.

4.2. External loads

In HFJOINT, the external loads involve nodal forces, surface tractions and imposed nodal displacements. Particularly, the users are allowed to define beam-element forces F_{ax} (axial force), F_{ips} (in-plane shear force), F_{ops} (out-of-plane shear force), T_b (torsional moment),

M_{ipb} (in-plane bending moment) and M_{opb} (out-of-plane bending moment), as shown in Fig. 17.

The resulting surface tractions acting on the loaded element faces are:

$$\vec{f}(x, y, z) = \left\{ \sum_{ax,ips,ops} \frac{F}{A} \vec{t}_a \right\} + \frac{T_b}{A} \vec{t}_r + \left\{ \sum_{ipb,opb} \frac{M}{I} y_c \vec{t}_b \right\} \quad (36)$$

where A is the area of cross section, I is the moment of inertia and y_c is the distance to the neutral surface. For each loaded element, the equivalent nodal force vector is then evaluated from the Gaussian numerical integral over the loaded faces. For instance, the equivalent nodal force vector resulting from a traction field applied on the surface $\zeta = 1$ is evaluated by:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\zeta=1}^{(l)} = \sum_{\xi} \sum_{\eta} \left\{ \mathbf{N}^T \bar{\mathbf{f}} \mid \det(\mathbf{J}_A) \mid w_i w_j \right\} \Big|_{\xi=\xi_i, \eta=\eta_j, \zeta=1} \quad (37)$$

Apart from the equivalent nodal forces converted from beam-element forces, the definition of an arbitrary nodal force vector is also allowed, denoted by $\mathbf{F}^{(n)}$. Considering total nodal forces:

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}^{(l)} + \mathbf{F}^{(n)} \quad (38)$$

applied on the model, the equilibrium equation takes the form:

$$\mathbf{K}\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{F} \quad (39)$$

which is the standard form of the static finite element formulation.

4.3. Boundary conditions

Based on this, imposed displacements can be considered for a group of selected DOFs denoted by \mathbf{U}_I , while the remaining free DOFs to be solved are denoted by \mathbf{U}_F . The equilibrium equation is then rewritten into the block matrix form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{FF} & \mathbf{K}_{FI} \\ \mathbf{K}_{IF} & \mathbf{K}_{II} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_F \\ \mathbf{U}_I \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{F}_F \\ \mathbf{F}_I \end{Bmatrix} \quad (40)$$

It should be mentioned that the additional external forces are not recommended for the imposed DOFs, i.e., $\mathbf{F}_I = \mathbf{0}$, because the forces applied on the imposed DOFs are usually dominated by the constraint forces. For the sake of generality, the entire displacement vector can be described by the least number of independent DOFs, inspired by the Lagrange's equation of the second kind:

$$\mathbf{U} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{I} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{Bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_F + \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{U}_I \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{P}\mathbf{U}_F + \mathbf{U}_{im} \quad (41)$$

where \mathbf{P} is a Boolean matrix by eliminating the columns corresponding to the imposed DOFs from an N -by- N identity matrix, and \mathbf{U}_{im} is the global imposed displacement vector (where the values for the free DOFs are left zero). Note that the fixed boundary condition is in fact a special case of the imposed displacement where the imposed value is zero.

4.4. Static solver

By substituting Eq. (41) into Eq. (39), the free DOFs are then solved:

$$\mathbf{U}_F = (\mathbf{P}^T \mathbf{K} \mathbf{P})^{-1} \mathbf{P}^T (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{K} \mathbf{U}_{im}) \quad (42)$$

The complete displacement vector can then be obtained by substituting the solved \mathbf{U}_F back into Eq. (41). For each element, the displacements at the element nodes \mathbf{U}_e are extracted from the global displacement vector \mathbf{U} . The stress at a given location (ξ, η, ζ) can then be evaluated from:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{B}(\xi, \eta, \zeta) \mathbf{U}_e \quad (43)$$

In the developed HFJOINT, the element stresses are firstly evaluated at the Gaussian points, resulting in σ_j (where j is taken from one to the total number of Gaussian points). Based on this, the nodal stresses can be obtained from an extrapolation. Given the assumption that the distribution of a stress field follows the superposition of element shape functions, the relationship between the stresses at the nodes $\sigma^{(n)}$ and Gaussian points $\sigma^{(G)}$ is formulated by:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(G)} = \mathbf{T}^{(\sigma)} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(n)} \quad (44)$$

where

$$T_{i,j}^{(\sigma)} = N_j(\xi_i, \eta_i, \zeta_i) \quad (45)$$

is the value of the j th shape function at the location of the i th Gaussian point. The inverse matrix of $\mathbf{T}^{(\sigma)}$, which has been explicitly derived in this work (see Appendix A), allows to extrapolate the stress from the Gaussian points to the nodes.

Based on the solved stress components at the nodes, the signed von Mises stress field is calculated from:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{vm} &= \text{sgn}(\sigma_{xx} + \sigma_{yy} + \sigma_{zz}) \\ &\times \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} [(\sigma_{xx} - \sigma_{yy})^2 + (\sigma_{yy} - \sigma_{zz})^2 + (\sigma_{zz} - \sigma_{xx})^2] + 3(\tau_{xy}^2 + \tau_{yz}^2 + \tau_{xz}^2)} \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

for an intuitive visualization, where the signs of the stresses are determined by the traces of their stress tensors which can be optionally considered during the plot. Within a given mesh grid, the nodal stresses may not be unique when the node is shared by multiple elements. From the extrapolation of different adjacent elements, slight deviations are inevitable. In order to avoid this, a dynamic list "node_stress" containing N_{nd} empty elements is initiated. For each element, the nodal stresses are collected into the list, and the average value of nodal stress is calculated. This will be finally passed into the class "ModelPlot" for the visualization of model deformation and stress field.

To determine the HSS stress at the weld toe, the local stresses at the extrapolation points need to be obtained. In HFJOINT, the stress tensor at a user-specified location (x, y, z) is calculated through interpolation of the surrounding stress field.

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(x, y, z) = N(\xi, \eta, \zeta) \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(e)} \quad (47)$$

where (ξ, η, ζ) are the natural coordinates of the point (x, y, z) in an element having the nodal coordinates:

$$\mathbf{r}^{(e)} = \{\bar{\mathbf{r}}_1^T, \bar{\mathbf{r}}_2^T, \dots, \bar{\mathbf{r}}_N^T\}^T \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 3} \quad (48)$$

Starting from an initial guess of the natural coordinates, e.g., $\xi = \eta = \zeta = 0.0$, these natural coordinates can be updated through the iteration below:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \xi_{new} \\ \eta_{new} \\ \zeta_{new} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{Bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \frac{dx}{d\xi} & \frac{dx}{d\eta} & \frac{dx}{d\zeta} \\ \frac{dy}{d\xi} & \frac{dy}{d\eta} & \frac{dy}{d\zeta} \\ \frac{dz}{d\xi} & \frac{dz}{d\eta} & \frac{dz}{d\zeta} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} x_{new} - x \\ y_{new} - y \\ z_{new} - z \end{Bmatrix} \quad (49)$$

in order to fulfill that:

$$\bar{\mathbf{r}} = N(\xi, \eta, \zeta) \bar{\mathbf{r}}^{(e)} \quad (50)$$

It is known that, for each element, the natural coordinates can always be solved. However, only the element containing the selected point is needed since the stress should be evaluated from interpolation inside the element instead of extrapolation from an outside element. Therefore, the iteration (Eq. (49)) is performed taking each element of the model, while the loop is interrupted and the result (ξ, η, ζ) is returned when the condition:

$$\max(|\xi|, |\eta|, |\zeta|) < 1.0 + \text{tol} \quad (51)$$

is satisfied. Note that a tolerance (taken as 0.2 by default) is considered allowing for a slight error of the given coordinates (x, y, z) (i.e., the specified point is slightly outside the model). By substituting the solved ξ, η, ζ back into Eq. (47), the stresses at the point (x, y, z) are then obtained.

4.5. Postprocessing for HSS stress and stress concentration factors

In finite element analysis, the local stress at the weld toe theoretically approaches infinity due to the numerical singularity from the

Fig. 18. Illustration of the linear extrapolation for the evaluation of HSS stress.

non-smooth feature. For the fatigue assessment of tubular joints, the standardized way of determining the fatigue governing stress at the weld toe is according to the surface stress extrapolation HSS stress approach as described by DNV-RP-C203 [29]. The hot-spot structural stress is computed by extrapolating local stresses extracted at nodes a few distances away from the weld toe (Fig. 18).

The stress concentration factor (SCF) can then be evaluated as the ratio between the HSS stress and the nominal stress:

$$SCF = \frac{\sigma_{HS}}{\sigma_{nm}} \quad (52)$$

where the nominal stresses are the axial stress or maximum bending stress evaluated based on a beam model, given by:

$$\sigma_{nm} = \begin{cases} \frac{F}{A} & \text{(axial loading case)} \\ \frac{M}{I} \cdot r & \text{(bending cases)} \end{cases} \quad (53)$$

The HSS stress of a tubular welded joint is estimated from the linear extrapolation of the stress field within the hot-spot zone:

$$\sigma_{HS} = \frac{x_2 \bar{\sigma}_1 - x_1 \bar{\sigma}_2}{x_2 - x_1} \quad (54)$$

where the distances of the local-stress points (i.e., x_1 and x_2 in Fig. 18) are selected following the DNV-RP-C203 standard [29], given by:

$$x_1 = 0.2\sqrt{rt} \quad (55)$$

$$x_2 = 0.65\sqrt{rt} \quad (56)$$

for the brace side, and

$$x_1 = 0.2\sqrt{rt} \quad (57)$$

$$x_2 = \begin{cases} 0.4\sqrt{rtRT} & \text{(for the crown zone)} \\ \pi R/36 & \text{(for the saddle zone)} \end{cases} \quad (58)$$

for the chord side. Due to the curvature of the chord, the local-stress points may lie slightly above the chord surface. Therefore, they are projected onto the exact outer surface of the chord as a correction. Since the local stress is a tensor involving six independent components for a 3D case, the scale values are required for $\bar{\sigma}_1$ and $\bar{\sigma}_2$ used in Eq. (54). In most practices, two types of stress fields are considered: the stress normal to the weld toe (which can also be derived from a practical measurement using strain gauges) and the maximum principal stress (which is often used for assessing fatigue lifetime). The former one is evaluated from:

$$\bar{\sigma} = n_i \sigma_{ij} n_j = n_x^2 \sigma_{xx} + n_y^2 \sigma_{yy} + n_z^2 \sigma_{zz} + 2n_x n_y \sigma_{xy} + 2n_x n_z \sigma_{xz} + 2n_y n_z \sigma_{yz} \quad (59)$$

where $\bar{n} = (n_x, n_y, n_z)$ is the local coordinate system shown in Fig. 4(a) and σ_{ij} is the stress tensor at the specified location. The maximum principal stress is obtained by taking the absolute maximum eigenvalue of the stress tensor σ_{ij} .

4.6. Overall workflow

Summarized from the above, the entire high-fidelity modeling and SCF analysis are based on five modules including model creation (Sections 2 and 3), load definition (Section 4.2), boundary conditions (Section 4.3), FE solver (Section 4.4) and postprocessing (Section 4.5). The overall workflow is illustrated in Fig. 19.

During the program computation, the units must be compatible for the involved parameters. The international system of units (SI) is used in the case studies following next.

5. Case studies

5.1. Case study I - stress concentration factor distribution of a T joint

In order to validate the developed HFJOINT numerical tool, a typical T joint (which was also used as a benchmark in [27,30,31]) is created for a verification with respect to the stress concentration factors near the weld. As shown in Fig. 20, the model is created using the Hexa27n elements. The geometric dimensions and mesh refinement can be seen from the figure.

The material properties are: the elastic modulus $E = 210$ GPa and the Poisson ratio $\nu = 0.33$. For the chord, both the end points are entirely fixed, i.e., the displacements of the nodes at $x = \pm 2065$ mm are all imposed to be zero, which are considered through the matrix \mathbf{P} plugged in Eq. (42). The joint is loaded at the free end of the brace. The load cases axial tension ($F = 1$ kN), in-plane bending ($M = 1$ kN m) and out-of-plane bending ($M = 1$ kN m) are firstly defined as beam-element forces, and are then converted into equivalent nodal forces of the high-fidelity Hexa27n model (see Fig. 21) by projecting the axial (or bending) stresses onto the shape-function space of each element.

The resulting von Mises stress fields with respect to axial tension, in-plane bending and out-of-plane bending are shown in Fig. 22.

For the hot-spot zone of the weld at the brace side, the stress state at a specified location can always be obtained from the interpolation (Eq. (47)) as long as the containing element and natural coordinates are found through Eq. (49). At a set of discrete polar angles ranging from 0° to 90° , such SCFs can always be evaluated by Eq. (52), using either the normal stress towards the weld toe or the maximum principal stress. Taking the transformed normal stress, the convergence of the Hexa27n model is first studied through considering different mesh refinements. The numbers of discretization segments n_p are taken 32, 48, 64 and 96 (corresponding to 16, 24, 32 and 48 Hexa27n elements, respectively). The resulting SCFs are shown in Fig. 23, where only half of the region, i.e., $\rho \in [0, 180^\circ]$ is provided because the numerical model is perfectly symmetric about the $z = 0$ plane.

It can be observed that the SCFs approximate the curves for $n_p = 96$ with increasing mesh refinement, confirming the convergence of the Hexa27n model. When refining the discretization along the weld circumference from 64 to 96 segments, the relative changes in SCFs are below 2%, which indicate the mesh convergence. Based on the discretization $n_p = 64$ of the weld circumference, an additional convergence analysis is performed for the radial mesh refinement of the outer C-HS region by considering the number of elements n_{out} from 1 to 4. The resulting SCFs under axial load (AX), in-plane bending (IPB) and out-of-plane bending (OPB) are presented in Table 1.

It can be observed that the SCF values on the brace side are very slightly affected by the mesh refinement, while the SCF values on the chord side, particularly at the saddle point (CS), show more noticeable changes as n_{out} increases. Even so, the relative change in SCF values is below 1.6% when n_{out} changes from 3 to 4. This confirms that a value of $n_{out} = 3$ is sufficient to describe the stress field of the hot-spot region and further refinement yields marginal improvement in accuracy. This is because, in HFJOINT, the stress fields in the Hexa27n elements are quadratically interpolated, and the stress field of the C-HS region can be well approximated.

Fig. 19. Overall workflow of HFJOINT involving five modules for model creation, load definition, boundary conditions, FE solver and postprocessing, respectively.

Fig. 20. Model of the example T joint created in the developed HFJOINT tool.

This case study is executed on a PC (Dell vPRO) with following configurations: CPU 13th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-1365U, Memory 16.0 GB 3200 MHz, Python 3.12.2. The stiffness matrices are stored in form of the compressed sparse row (csr) matrix. By default, they are no longer saved after the nodal displacements have been solved (Eq. (42)). During the analysis, the cost of computational power is summarized in Table 2.

With increasing n_p , the memory cost increases, but slightly less than proportional with n_p due to the sparse feature. However, the CPU time significantly increases, especially for the evaluation of the global stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_g and the nodal stresses σ_n , because the inverse of the Jacobian matrix needs to be evaluated at each Gaussian point of each element. For similar cases, the value $n_p = 64$ will be recommended considering the trade off between accuracy (recall Fig. 23) and computational efficiency. By fitting a least-squares line in the

Fig. 21. Mapping from beam-element force to nodal forces at the loaded cross section: (a) axial force; (b) in-plane bending moment; (c) out-of-plane bending moment.

Fig. 22. The signed von Mises stress field (unit: MPa) of the example T joints subjected to: (a) axial loading; (b) in-plane bending; (c) out-of-plane bending.

Table 1

Convergence of the SCFs with respect to the mesh refinement for the outer side of the C-HS region.

n_{out}	AX				IPB		OPB	
	BS	BC	CS	CC	BC	CC	BS	CS
1	8.12	1.53	11.26	4.34	1.52	3.17	8.10	12.16
2	8.07	1.52	14.16	4.84	1.51	3.52	8.06	15.27
3	8.06	1.52	15.27	4.52	1.51	3.28	8.05	16.61
4	8.06	1.52	15.02	4.49	1.51	3.25	8.05	16.36

($\log_{10} n_{DOF}, \log_{10} T_{CPU}$), the complexity of the entire work flow is estimated as $\mathcal{O}(N^{1.89})$, which is slightly lower than $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ in most standard finite element analysis [32]. This is benefited from the lightweight feature of the HFJOINT solver and the efficient computation with csr

matrices. Considering both the normal stress (after the coordinate transform using Eq. (59)) and the maximum principal stress, the resulting SCFs at the brace and chord sides are computed, as shown in Fig. 24.

The results are further compared with a benchmark model developed in Abaqus version v2019 (having an unstructured mesh using 20-node brick elements, C3D20R) [27], where the SCF distributions are investigated (see the blue area) based on a group of parameter ranges. From the figures, it can be seen that the SCFs evaluated from the normal stress to the weld toe and the maximum principal stress are close to each other, because the stress is dominated by the bending normal stress. Exemptions are the SCFs in the weld crown regions for the in-plane bending case (Fig. 24(e)) due to the significant shear stress component which contributes to the maximum principal stress. It is also worth mentioning that, for the in-plane bending case, the normal stress is perfectly zero at the saddle (see the SCFs at 90° and 270°

Fig. 23. Convergence of the SCFs with improving mesh refinement: (a) axial tension (brace side); (b) in-plane bending (brace side); (c) out-of-plane bending (brace side); (d) axial tension (chord side); (e) in-plane bending (chord side); (f) out-of-plane bending (chord side).

Table 2

Summary of the computational cost for the axial loaded case.

n_ρ	Number of DOFs		Sparsity of $K_{g,bc}$	Memory cost for $K_{g,bc}$ (MB)	CPU time (s)			
	K_g	$K_{g,bc}$			K_g	$K_{g,bc}$	U_g	σ_n
32	26 388	25 740	0.5505%	41.84	21.13	1.51	5.06	10.94
48	36 360	35 640	0.3988%	58.11	50.32	3.92	9.14	27.47
64	46 620	45 828	0.3108%	74.86	50.80	3.60	31.50	24.09
96	68 004	67 068	0.2128%	109.79	108.32	9.64	71.63	60.58

Fig. 24. The stress concentration factors along the weld circumference of the example T joint: (a) axial tension (brace side); (b) in-plane bending (brace side); (c) out-of-plane bending (brace side); (d) axial tension (chord side); (e) in-plane bending (chord side); (f) out-of-plane bending (chord side).

Table 3
Calculation of mandatory modeling parameters for X and K example joints.

Joint	Parameters from Ref.						HFJOINT input			
	D	τ	β	γ	α	θ	r_{brace}	t_{chord}	t_{brace}	L_{chord}
X (E30)	508 mm	0.79	0.38	20.7	9.8	90°	96.52 mm	12.27 mm	9.69 mm	2.489 m
K (K-4)	216 mm	0.88	0.47	13.5	10.2	60°	50.76 mm	8.00 mm	7.04 mm	1.266 m

Table 4
The SCFs of the X- and K-joints evaluated from HFJOINT (based on the transformed normal stresses, Eq. (59)) with comparison to the experimental results [33].

Joint	Approach	AX				IPB				OPB			
		BC	BS	CC	CS	BC	BS	CC	CS	BC	BS	CC	CS
X (E30)	HFJOINT	0.4	7.6	4.5	21.3	1.7	0.0	4.2	0.0	0.0	4.4	0.0	12.2
	Experiment	1.5	10.6	3.3	21.8	2.5	–	4.4	–	–	3.8	–	7.7
K (K-4)	HFJOINT	1.0	2.2	6.5	5.6	1.7	0.0	3.4	0.7	0.0	3.3	0.0	8.6
	Experiment	–	2.3	5.4	3.6	–	–	–	–	–	2.9	–	6.8

in Figs. 24(b) and 24(e)), and for the out-of-plane bending case, the normal stress is perfectly zero at the crown (see the SCFs at 0° and 180° in Figs. 24(c) and 24(f)). This is caused by the neutral surfaces of the bending deformations given that the brace is rather slender. Moreover, the SCF curves (absolute values) are all symmetric about a 180° shift, since the model is geometrically symmetric about the plane $x = 0$.

For the SCF distributions at the brace side, the results from HFJOINT fall well within the envelope of the benchmark model [27]. In [27], constrained optimizations were performed at each polar angle to achieve the minimum and maximum weld cross-section areas within the AWS recommendations. Such optimization is not included in this work. The weld features are taken $R_w = 0.6T = 7.62$ mm and $\phi_w = 45^\circ$ for the entire circumference, yielding in the cross-section area overall close to (at places, even slightly higher than) the maximum case of the AWS recommendations. The SCFs of the HFJOINT model are therefore slightly closer to the lower boundaries of the benchmark model, especially for the IPB case. For the SCF distributions at the chord side, the blue values are constrained within narrow ranges due to their lower sensitivities to the weld geometric parameters. Considering the discrepancy resulting from the optimization, the SCF distributions evaluated from HFJOINT overall show good agreement with the benchmark model. From the above comparison, the reliability of the developed HFJOINT tool is confirmed.

5.2. Case example II - stress concentration factors of X- and K-joints

In order to further validate the SCFs calculated using HFJOINT, X- and K-joints are selected from [33] where a database of experimental results is provided. From the chord diameter and the remaining non-dimensional parameters characterizing the geometric features of the joints, the parameters required for HFJOINT modeling inputs are calculated and provided in Table 3. The material properties are the same as defined in Section 5.1.

Except for the mandatory parameters, the chord length L_{chord} is also specified since it has been provided in the literature. Additionally, the optional parameter $n_\rho = 64$ and $n_{\text{out}} = 3$ are selected referring to the mesh convergence studied in Section 5.1. For the chord, the nodes on the end cross sections are fully constrained as the boundary conditions of the model. The load conditions axial tension (AX), in-plane bending moment (IPB) and out-of-plane bending moment (OPB) are considered. For the X joint, the loads are symmetrically applied on both the braces, in order to be consistent with the balanced load mentioned in the literature. The von Mises stress fields are then solved, as shown in Fig. 25.

For each load case, the SCFs along the weld circumference, with respect to both the brace and chord sides, can be obtained by following the HFJOINT workflow, where the normal stresses after the coordinate

transform (Eq. (59)) are taken. In Table 4, the SCF values at the crown and saddle points are listed, and are compared with test data provided in literature [33].

From Table 4, it can be concluded that the SCFs analyzed from HFJOINT align well with the experimental data for most loading cases and positions. For example, under AX and IPB loading, the SCF deviations at most of the positions are below 10%, and in several cases (e.g., AX-CC and IPB-CC), the differences are even below 5%. Meanwhile, a few discrepancies can still be noted. For instance, in OPB conditions, the SCFs at the chord (saddle side) are always higher, where the deviation may reach up to 40%. This may possibly be caused by inevitable deviations in positioning the strain gauges used to calculate the experimental SCF values, as well as due to the real geometry of the weld which has a sensitive effect on the local stress field. Despite this, the overall agreement confirms the reliability of HFJOINT for analyzing local stress distribution features in welded tubular joints, showing its potential for fatigue assessment of complex joints having diverse configurations.

6. Conclusions

In this study, a high-fidelity numerical modeling tool, HFJOINT, is developed for the SCF analysis of welded tubular joints. Compared with general finite element analysis tools (and softwares), the developed tool supports for the structured mesh of elementary joints, the creation of complex 3D joints, the mapping from beam-element forces to Hexa27n nodal forces, the extraction of local stress at an arbitrary point and the evaluation of weld SCFs at both the chord and brace sides, from a semi-automatic and user-friendly approach. Especially, the following points are remarked:

1. The Hexa27n mesh of an elementary joint can be generated automatically as long as the mandatory parameters (the radius and thickness of chord and brace, as well as the intersection angle) are defined. The values of the remaining optional parameters will be taken by default rules if not specified.
2. For the load mapping from beam-element force to the Hexa27n nodal forces, the element nodal force vectors are evaluated by considering the exact distributions of axial, shear and bending stresses acting on the loaded cross section.
3. The SCFs can be evaluated from either the maximum principal stress or the transformed normal stress perpendicular to the weld toe. The local stress points are automatically selected according to the DNV [29] recommendations.
4. The developed HFJOINT tool is validated through comparison with the SCFs of the benchmark T-, K- and X- joints obtained from simulation results and test data reported in literature,

Fig. 25. The von Mises stress fields (unit: MPa) of the example joints (where the deformations are largely scaled in order to be visible): (a)(b)(c) X joint; (d)(e)(f) K joint; (a)(d) axial tension; (b)(e) in-plane bending; (c)(f) out-of-plane bending.

confirming its feasibility and potential in fatigue assessment of broader practical welded tubular joints.

Based on the developed GUI, a beta version of HFJOINT will soon be available online. The documentation has been made available on the Github website [34] and will be periodically updated.

It should be noted that the current version of HFJOINT is developed under the assumption of linear elastic analysis, without considering plastic deformation, crack propagation or geometric imperfections. The weld geometry is idealized, ignoring as-built weld profile variations. The linear extrapolation of stress as recommended by standards may result in underestimated HSS and SCFs in cases with steep stress gradients. Future developments will aim to enrich HFJOINT by including the multi-scale modeling techniques [35] for weld profile irregularities [36], fatigue crack growth analysis [37] and lifetime assessment [13]. The tool will also be regularly updated to be compatible with state-of-the-art standards and methods. All of this will enable more accurate modeling and reliable fatigue assessment of welded tubular joints in broader practical applications.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Songhan Zhang: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Wim De Waele:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation. **Kris Hectors:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Project administration, Investigation, Data curation, Methodology, Resources.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Table B.1

Geometric parameters (in alphabetical order) defined for the mesh generation of an elementary joint (Note that the mandatory parameters marked with * do not have default values and must therefore be provided from the users).

Variable description	Default value	Unit
*Brace inclination angle (required)	–	deg
Edge length of the C-PL-CT part (circumferential)	$2r/3$	m
Transit factor of the B-TR region	1.20	–
Transit factor of the C-TR region	1.15	–
Node interval along the axis of the B-HS region	$3t/n_{bhs}$	m
Edge length of the C-PL-CT part (axial)	$2r/3$	m
Edge length of the C-TR region (axial)	$3.5(r+t)$	m
Edge length of the C-TR region (circumferential)	$3.5(r+t)$	m
Length of the B-UN region	$0.25L$	m
Axial length of the B-TR region	$0.25L$	m
Total length of the chord	$2b_{cts}$	m
Number of intervals in the B-UN region	6	–
Number of node intervals in the C-HS region (outward)	6	–
Number of node intervals in the C-HS region (interior)	4	–
Number of nodes along the radius of the C-TR region	5	–
Number of nodes along the radius of the C-PL-TR part	5	–
Number of nodes along the axis of the C-EXT-Xn/Xp part	5	–
Number of nodes along the circumference of the C-EXT-Zn/Zp part	5	–
Number of node intervals along the weld circumference	32	–
Number of nodes through the chord thickness	2	–
Number of intervals along the axis of the B-TR region	10	–
Number of intervals along the radial direction of the weld	2	–
Number of intervals along the upward direction of the weld	2	–
Number of intervals along the axis of the B-HS region	6	–
Inclined angle for the upper edge of the weld cross section	$\pi/6$	rad
The gap between the C-PL region and the weld toe	$2.0T$	m
The gap in height between the chord and the brace	$0.6t$	m
*Outer radius of the brace (required)	–	m
*Outer radius of the chord (required)	–	m
*Wall thickness of the brace (required)	–	m
*Wall thickness of the chord (required)	–	m
The gap between the C-TR region and the weld toe	$2.0T$	m

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